

Digital transformation within Universities

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1. INTRODUCTION

From the beginning of 2020, COVID-19 has become a major issue for the entire society. Many uncertainties have arisen and fast changes had to be made in many organizations. The crisis has had a big impact on many branches in the job market as well as the university.

The demand for office space has declined since the beginning of the COVID-19 crisis. Therefore, there will be a shift from structured office environments to more flexible, virtual, and home-based work arrangements (Megahed, N. A., & Ghoneim, E. M. 2020), which could result in many empty office spaces. This is also an important issue for Universities. There is still uncertainty and a lack of knowledge how organizations and universities should react towards these developments in the real estate branch (Ferdig, R. E., Baumgartner, E., Hartshorne, R., Kaplan-Rakowski, R., & Mouza, C. 2020).

Currently, the maximum number of journeys and institutions with the purpose of teaching is only 20% of the normal number at Tilburg University (Tilburg University, 2020). The majority of students and teachers may not be physically present at the university. Tilburg University has to deal with these changes in a short time to solve the problem during the COVID-19 crisis. This will lead to a shift from physical classes to online classes. Furthermore, during the crisis two years worth of digital transformation was conducted in only two months (Vromans, 2020).

To investigate this shift within the University, a case study of Tilburg University is conducted. This paper has been divided into four parts, the first part will focus on the research approach of the paper. The second part will give a sector analysis of the housing and real estate branch. After the sector analysis, this paper will address specific analysis focussing on Cybersecurity, Business Process Integration, and IT Governance & strategic sourcing. Lastly, the researchers will give a conclusion of the conducted research.

2. RESEARCH

2.1 Objective

As mentioned in the introduction, COVID-19 has led to uncertainties in the housing and real estate branch. Approximately only 20% of the space on campus is available for teaching since teachers are working from home and students follow online lectures remotely. Consequently, if 20% of the total space is occupied at the campus, then 80% of the campus is not effectively used by the University itself. The knowledge that is missing for the housing and real estate branch constitutes the changes in value creation dimension from the digital transformation framework. The university managed to provide students

study material and continuation of their lectures through the use of online communication tools. Moreover, online proctoring has been applied as a measure to control students during their exams. Therefore, the University has been ambitious enough to learn new digital methods.

However, the University needs to think how to create revenue from future business operations if lecture rooms and University offices become obsolete for the education of students. Moreover, it should be investigated what the future business scope will be if Tilburg University will not require 80% of the campus space anymore. As such, knowledge is needed in order to respond rapidly to the change of supply and demand in the housing and real estate industry. Therefore, the following research question is formulated: *What effect do fast changing environments have on the digital transformation within universities?*

2.2 Approach

The first attempt was to provide data to base the research on the case study Tilburg University. The next step will be to provide more information through meetings with professors related to this research each Wednesday on the campus at Tilburg University. These meetings are inspiration resources for the research and will help further the progress of writing this term paper. In case professors are unavailable on campus, zoom meetings will be held if there are any questions related to this paper. Resources are mainly provided from databases such as Google Scholar and world bank to treat data. Since the topic of this term paper is based on Tilburg University, the final sample will only consist of data in Tilburg. For the sampling method, we have chosen to perform a convenience sampling method due to the pandemic. Nowadays, physical contact has been reduced to a minimum, therefore, there is no alternative sampling method. The experiences of students at Tilburg University before COVID-19 and during COVID-19 will also be used as resources. Moreover, the meetings with the professors will also provide data by sharing their experiences with technology for teaching and online learning. Since the data in this paper is based on students' and professors' experiences, the gathered information is possibly inconsistent due to different opinions. However, to minimize the impact of limitations due to COVID-19, the cases in the sample will consist of different students and professors at Tilburg University. Therefore, the research method is a cross-sectional study. Unfortunately, the research strategy that has the lowest

level of internal validity for generating evidence regarding a causal effect is the cross-sectional study. The extent to which the outcome of this study is applicable to other Universities is low. The obtained results in a sample of the population can not be statistical generalized. Thus, the external validity is low.

3. REAL ESTATE AND HOUSING

3.1 Sector introduction

In general, the real estate market is known for certain cycle trends, reaching big heights or low lows. The real estate market was entering an 'uncharted territory', for instance the United States market is now in the longest economic expansion since the start of measuring in the 1850s (Deloitte, 2019). This has resulted in uncertainty about the length of the economic expansion cycle. Consequently, an unexpected event can happen, which economic experts did not predict. According to Teuben and Neshat (2020) the market size of the professionally managed global real estate investments increased from \$8.9 trillion in 2018 to \$9.6 trillion in 2019. This is consistent with the economic expansion cycle mentioned by Deloitte.

The real estate market has several interdependencies. Financial markets, town planning and urban policies are being examined for major cities (Theurillat, Rérat, & Crevoisier, 2013). Financial institutions are focused on setting up a constant source of long-term profit, thereby they can be seen as the main players in this market. Real estate analysts and experts inspect a local market and evaluate potential properties. Portfolio managers or property developers are other parties which could be involved in this market and can be seen as professional investors. These key players have mutual relationships with local authorities, political parties, commercial operators and future users (Theurillat et al., 2013). Changes in the economic expansion cycle may affect these relationships.

3.2 Key developments

Based on an article by PWC, COVID-19 has accelerated certain trends on the real estate market. Three key issues have arisen since the outbreak of COVID-19. The first issue is rent shortfalls, one-third of US residential renters missed their April rent payments. The second issue consists of financing challenges, which is caused by the declining value of property. The third issue is disruption in securitization markets: spreads on real estate securities have been widening (PricewaterhouseCoopers, 2020).

Deloitte has also published an article about considerations to take for the real estate industry. Focusing on the office market they had mentioned among others the following long-term impacts (Deloitte, 2020): More people will work remotely and flexibly, businesses seeking new office accommodations will require less desk-space per worker, and there will be greater investments in IT resilience to promote remote working.

When companies want to tackle these issues related to COVID-19 they will have to deal with long-term strategic questions according to PWC (PricewaterhouseCoopers, 2020). One of these questions is how companies should redesign their offices and

workplaces. What to do with remote workers, and does this mean that the firm will need less physical office space? Another question is about changes in the urbanizations trends: investors may want to focus more on suburbs and rural locations.

The third question regards the rent prices, which may drop because of unexpected excess of unoccupied space: companies may want to review their capital structure.

3.3 Specific focus

Desk research towards the real estate sector has shown several key developments due to COVID-19. The developments all have in common that there are changes in demand and supply in the real estate sector related to the crisis. PWC and Deloitte both mentioned remote working and changing urbanization trends.. There is a lack of knowledge towards the key developments in this sector, especially about the way companies deal with these rapid changes in supply and demand. In this research will focus on the digital transformations related to the key developments. A case study within Tilburg University was conducted and information is gathered from an online interview with the CIO of Tilburg University.

4. ANALYSIS

4.1 IT Governance and Strategic Sourcing

The IT Governance aspect of this case is relevant for indicating governance issues caused by this rapid digital transformation due to COVID-19. Pre-, current- and post-COVID-19 situations are described. The IT Governance matrix was the base upon describing the changes on IT Governance level, caused by the disruption. *There is a focus on Tilburg University for elaborating differences in governance levels.*

4.1.1 IT Governance within universities

Previous studies show that decentralized IT as a part of the organisational structure is seen as a high risk, since it is preferred by most institutions to fully control IT (Bianchi, Sousa, Pereira, & Luciano, 2017). Universities with a decentralized structure face several problems. For instance a duplication of resources, difficulties in achieving strategic alignment with business objectives and IT risks not being managed. There is only a positive effect when educational IT capabilities of the different business units (faculties) are also provided with decentralized IT supporting services. Nevertheless, centralized IT is preferred by most institutions since it enables them to maintain control over the decentralized IT functions in different faculties (Bianchi et al., 2017).

Bianchi et al. (2017) researched the IT Governance structures of several universities around the world (Brazil, Portugal and the Netherlands), by interviewing IT directors and CIO's. Since the case study is focused on Tilburg University, governance perspectives from the universities based in the Netherlands are the most relevant for this research. Both CIO's from Dutch universities mention that IT Governance is centralized with a federal structure that enables it. The main benefits of centralisation are economies on skills and applications, standardization and cost reduction.

Jairak and Praneetpolgrang (2013) state that there is a limited amount of university-oriented IT governance frameworks. Furthermore, it was concluded that IT Governance implementations within universities do not differ that much from the way other industries operate. Based on this conclusion “Top Performers” (Weill, 2004) within the IT Governance matrix can be assessed towards characteristics from universities and more specifically, Tilburg University.

Weill (2004) describes three top performing governance types within organisations. As mentioned above, a centralized IT Governance strategy is desirable for universities, as well for Tilburg University. Furthermore, there is a federal structure where the business and C-level executives decide the business needs for the university, where in some cases the IT executives participate in the decision making. Therefore, the first of the three top performing governance types fit best for Tilburg University. Using this governance structure helps to prevent duplication of resources as well as difficulties in achieving strategic alignment with business objectives and IT risks.

Tilburg University had a limited budget to invest in information technology, although the limit was temporarily removed.

Changes in Value creation: digitizing is used within Tilburg University to support the primary processes. The digital transformation can be an opportunity to replace physical processes to save costs. The switch to more digital classes can reduce the demand for physical classrooms. Value is created via an online environment.

Use of technology: in the situation before COVID-19, digital lectures were not part of the strategy of Tilburg University (Vromans, 2020). However, during the crisis period, the university was forced to switch to a more flexible and digital environment. Due to the enforced changes, the university now sees opportunities to adopt digital innovations into their business model. Digital transformation can not be ignored for the new strategy of Tilburg University because this could lead to new opportunities for the IT department of the university and will influence the governance principles.

4.1.3 Changes in the ITG Matrix

During the COVID-19 crisis, the governance within Tilburg University was shifted from central to decentral. There were more decentralized initiatives by employees, serving students’ needs. An example will be provided in the Business Process part. The shift could lead to a change in the governance strategy of Tilburg University, where IT gets more participation in the decision making of the Business needs and IT principles of the organization. A decentralized governance structure fits best to the changing demands of the different business units (faculties). There was more demand for specific business applications, over 100 initiatives were on the backlog. To fit local demand, a decentralized and flexible IT application is necessary. Since there are so many initiatives on the backlog, a centralized view on business application needs is required. IT will become more involved in decision making than before COVID (Vromans, 2020). IT is no longer an additional actor.

Figure 1 (Weill,2004)

4.1.2 Digital transformation

According to Vial (2019), a digital transformation is “a process that aims to improve an entity by triggering significant changes to its proper through combinations of information, computing, communication, and connectivity technologies”. The digital transformation of Tilburg University is reviewed by the digital transformation matrix of Matt, Hess, & Benlian (2015). The different components of the model were assessed based on the COVID influences.

Structural changes dimensions: during COVID-19 the CIO and head of IT services were responsible for the digital transformation of Tilburg University. In the period of the COVID-19 crisis, many changes in the digital environment of Tilburg University were necessary (Vromans, 2020). Examples include new software licences, online examinations and the expansion of several IT services. These changes had to be taken care of to continue the primary processes of Tilburg University. The changes were not yet integrated into the existing strategy of the university. The digital transformation of Tilburg University was not expected and these changes were not structurally implemented. However, these changes will be important for a new strategic plan of Tilburg University (Brandenburg & Mee, 2020).

Financial aspects: during the COVID-19 crisis, money was not the driver to undergo a digital transformation. The purpose of the digital transformation was to continue the primary processes of the university.

4.2 Business Process Integration

This subchapter analyses changes during the COVID pandemic. This is done by analysing the pre-, during and post-COVID phases. First a UML case diagram is clarified, in the second part of this subchapter three UML activity diagrams are shown and explained.

4.2.1 UML Case Diagram

Figure 2 illustrates the representation of the student’s and professor’s interaction with the IT department and Real Estate department. This shows the relationship between the student/professor and different use cases they are involved in. This simplified and graphical representation shows three relationships: student-IT Department, Professor-IT department and professor-Real Estate department.

In order to follow lectures and supply study material, three use cases are required. First of all, the student needs a student account which is provided through the IT Department after being enrolled in the University.

This means that the IT Department creates a new student account for each new enrolled student with a password. Secondly, the student needs access to the online platforms and study tools supplied by the IT department. Simultaneously, the professor also uses the same platforms/tools as well as probably a few more than the student. Access to these platforms/tools for the professor should also be given by the IT department. Furthermore, the IT department is responsible for the security and maintenance of these platforms. Lastly, space on the campus is necessary in order to attend or give lectures such as lecture rooms and other facilities at the University. The real estate department should rethink how to use the space on campus to meet students' and professors' needs.

Figure 2 - UML case diagram

4.2.2 Three UML activity diagrams

A UML Activity diagram is created to compare how the key processes had to change due to the pandemic and what the expectations are based on the needs of students and professors.

The first diagram illustrates a normal student's school day before the pandemic happened. The activities a student does on a daily basis include, for example visiting the supermarket, attending a lecture, working on assignments, taking a lunch break and studying in the library. Other actions a student takes are: walking to the supermarket, lecture hall, toilet, workplace, lunchroom and library. The IT department gives the students and professors access to their account for Canvas, Wifi and library visits. The professor has similar actions as the student, but not as many. The only difference is that the professor gives the lecture instead of attending one and he visits his office afterwards. The University provides the users lecture halls, toilets, workplaces and a library. Other facilities the University has are a supermarket on the campus, AH to go, and a central lunchroom for everybody to use.

Figure 3 - PRE COVID (see appendix 1 for readable version)

The second diagram illustrates the situation during COVID-19, which shows that two factors out of five are removed and have become obsolete. This is mostly due to the absence of students, but also professors and other employees of the University. During the pandemic, education is online, manageable through the Canvas

system and Zoom sessions. Moreover, students collaborate in groups through Google Drive, OneDrive and other tools for remote communication. The diagram also shows the changes while the activities stay the same. However, the actions changed, for example making breakfast and lunch, starting computer, laptop or other devices, joining Zoom sessions and updating the students by email. Furthermore, the amount of tasks has increased for the IT department. Before COVID-19 occurred, the IT department only gave access to account/WIFI and library, but now it also provides licences for zoom sessions and the VPN portal. Lectures which are recorded also need to be secured and uploaded by the IT department if the professor and University approve recorded lectures.

Figure 4 - DURING COVID (see appendix 1 for readable version)

The third diagram illustrates the predictions of the situation after COVID-19. Since students, professors and other employees are used to working from home, there is a high chance that this method is more efficient and preferred. However, many others also wish for the pandemic to vanish as soon as possible in order to get back to normal life. This process might take longer than expected since the government is currently dealing with the prevention of the second wave of this pandemic. The expectation is that through the digital transformation with for example room booking systems people will slowly combine work from home and work on campus. This booking system will only allow a maximum capacity of students and professors on campus if interaction is more efficient or necessary. Therefore, the diagram shows that students can attend lectures on campus while doing self-study and group assignments can be done at home or via zoom. In case students prefer to work on their assignments in groups on campus, the booking system allows them to book an empty room beforehand which also shows the maximum number of students in the room. Therefore, students can still keep in compliance with security measures..

Figure 5 - POST COVID (see appendix 1 for readable version)

From the UML use case and activity diagrams can be concluded that there will be changes in the way of working for both students, IT department, professors, facility management and the University itself. Most importantly, a few factors vanished during COVID-19. University and other facilities reduced the amount of space needed for education. Therefore, the largest impact is on unoccupied areas at Tilburg University. However, teaching, learning and working in groups will not change, but the way of teaching and working in groups is changing. An example of this changing environment and way of

working is a booking system, this can be found in the POST-COVID activity diagram. This booking system let's a student reservate a study/workplace on campus and makes sure that certain security measures are taken into account.

4.3 Cyber Security

Security changes

The situation concerning COVID-19 has created a radical change from schooling on the campus to the digital environment. The government has taken measures to reduce the impact of the virus, which limits the university to provide physical education. However, there was hardly any time for preparation to technology, the fundamental enabler of the shift. Therefore, new challenges appeared along with the increased number of cyberthreats. This has partly to do with the user awareness and safeguards, which leave those vulnerable in the context of online education (Furnell & Shah, 2020). In general, as the network of digital users is growing hackers take advantage of the situation. Cybercriminals are changing their methods to adapt to the uncertainty, which has been created in this event. This adaptation is done through a passive course of action, such as fake messages as well as more aggressive methods, such as cyberattacks. According to Rosenbaum (2020) an increase of 40% is detected concerning cyber scams. The rising level of these cyber criminal activities takes place in the light of COVID-19. There are two areas in which these security risk problems are embedded. The first area can be acknowledged at the server of the university. As users from home are trying to access applications and data of the university, a connection is made without the protection of the campus network (Mohsin, 2020). The second area can be recognized by the user themselves. The users who are working from home do not have the same security systems or measures on their networks as they would have within the university. Therefore, the network poses a vulnerability which can be exploited by hackers (Mohsin, 2020)

Risk assessment

The cyber security risk is assessed through the use of the 5 steps model which is illustrated in figure 6.

Figure 6. (Refsdal et al., 2015)

The first step concerns the situation and the different events which have taken place. The shift to digital platforms due to COVID-19 results in an increase in the usage and reliance on technology. Systems are accessed through online platforms, in which the internet is used as a medium. Consequently, own devices and infrastructures are used, thus creating possible vulnerabilities and rising risks for cyber attacks.

In step two the risk within the university of Tilburg is addressed. In these times, five risks are identified from both security areas. As introduced above, the first risk is the remote access. The second risk is malware & phishing attacks, which concern fake messages or malicious software which damages the system or steals data from the user. The third risk is that employees may abandon security measures: as mentioned above awareness is a concerning issue. The fourth risk is unanticipated staff shortages or unintentional staff error due to the lack of preparation as a consequence of the sudden shift to home education. Lastly, there is the cyber attack risk. Human abstractions have led to backdoors in the system, which cybercriminals use to infiltrate the system (Mohsin, 2020).

The third step concerns the risk analysis, in which the risk is ranked according likelihood and impact. In the table down below a legend of the risks is provided. These will be further elaborated in the Cyber Security Report.

Legend

- R1: Remote access risk
- R2: Malware and phishing attack risk
- R3: Employees abandoning security measures
- R4: Unanticipated staff shortages
- R5: Cyber attack risk

In step four, each risk mentioned in step three is evaluated and provided with measures, and immediate actions.

In the last step, security measures are presented to mitigate the risk. The first security measure is the appliance of an incident response procedure. A detailed, well-practised, and flexible incident response plan ensures versatile adaptation on every issue in order to effectively minimize the impact to systems (Davis et al., 2008). The second security measure that can be enforced is the appliance of a multi-factor authentication. This method provides an additional layer of security for the network of university Tilburg. Therefore, sensitive information such as exams can be accessed in a robustly secure way (Sarginson, 2020).

5. DISCUSSION

The findings in this study suggests that there will be a shift to more remote working within Tilburg University, even after the COVID-19 crisis. The crisis has made the University aware of the possibilities for remote

working, which can possibly be adopted into the new strategy of Tilburg University.

The most important finding from the IT Governance part of the report is the shift in governance structure of Tilburg University. The university has changed from a centralized structure to a more decentralized governance structure. During the COVID-19 crisis, many decisions were made on a decentral level, because the business units had different needs.

The results of this study also show that there will be a change in the way of working for students, the IT department, professors as well as for the University itself. This change is a result of the shift from physical classes to online classes due to the COVID-19 crisis. In the future, the University will have to combine both remote working and physical classes into its strategy.

Due to the shift towards more remote working, there will be an increased risk of cyber threats. There is a growing number of data breaches related to working from home. Tilburg University has to change its risk mitigation strategy to respond to possible cyber treats. Staff is a very important asset to prevent cyber risks for the University. In addition, this report argued that employees are less likely to follow safe data practices while working from home.

During the COVID-19 crisis, decisions were made in a shorter time than before the crisis, two years worth of digital transformation was conducted in only two months. It can therefore be assumed that there will be possible implications in the processing of these decisions. Also, there was a shift in the day-to-day routines of students and professors. Students and professors became more dependent on the systems and online platforms of the University, to give and attend the online classes. As the professors and students had to work remotely, they used their own devices and networks to get access to the systems. This may result in cybersecurity risks for the university.

As mentioned before, online lecturers will be included in the new strategy of Tilburg University. To further support this strategy, business processes of the students and professors had to be adjusted, and cybersecurity risks had to be mitigated. If there will be a new crisis, the IT department would be more flexible to anticipate this crisis with their systems. After the crisis, there will be a shift from structured office environments to more flexible, virtual, and home-based work arrangements. Furthermore, because online lecturers have become more important within the primary process of the university, it is important that the defined risks will be mitigated. This could be an important issue for future research.

6. CONCLUSION

This report ends with the lessons that were learned about this digital transformation. The shift to remote working due to COVID-19 has influenced organizations and their employees and customers in different ways. Based on this report, new insights on the changes in real estate usage within universities were gathered. The research is limited to only one university; therefore, the generalizability has not been proven. Other universities or types of organizations were not included in this research. Furthermore, the ratio between remote versus physical working is not determined for the future.

This report is not based on longitudinal research outcomes and as such the value of the outcomes could be valuable for only a short amount of time. Earlier in the report, it was mentioned that two years worth of digital transformation was conducted in only two months. Therefore, it is less likely that the pre-COVID-19 state will return within Tilburg University. In contrast, the current state could change rapidly and influence the digital transformation even further. This uncertainty requires continuous research towards the manner in which organizations deal with the shift towards remote working and the influence on governance structures, business processes and cybersecurity risks. Future research could focus on changes in governance structures in other organizations, for instance the shift from centralization towards decentralization, as companies must be agile and resilient for disruptions. Another angle could be to investigate how different organizations schedule real estate usage. Lastly, it is necessary to pay attention to research on the growing amount of data breaches related to home working, since it is expected to be one of the main permanent outcomes of the digital transformation.

7. REFERENCES

- Bianchi, I. S., Sousa, R. D., Pereira, R., & Luciano, E. (2017). IT Governance Structures in Brazilian, Dutch and Portuguese Universities. Retrieved from [https://pdf.sciencedirectassets.com/280203/1-s2.0-S1877050917X00203/1-s2.0-S1877050917323220/main.pdf?X-Amz-Security-Token=IQoJb3JpZ2luX2VjEjH%2F%2F%2F%2F%2F%2F%2F%2FwEaCXVzLWVhc3QtMSJHMEUCIQRDwmCKaIb2tZefH3a8Nyfc7ls%2FgegXq%2Bg9nIRLVWISNvAIGK4USjn%2](https://pdf.sciencedirectassets.com/280203/1-s2.0-S1877050917X00203/1-s2.0-S1877050917323220/main.pdf?X-Amz-Security-Token=IQoJb3JpZ2luX2VjEjH%2F%2F%2F%2F%2F%2F%2F%2F%2FwEaCXVzLWVhc3QtMSJHMEUCIQRDwmCKaIb2tZefH3a8Nyfc7ls%2FgegXq%2Bg9nIRLVWISNvAIGK4USjn%2)
- Deloitte. (2019). *Uncharted territory*. Retrieved from <https://www2.deloitte.com/content/dam/Deloitte/us/Documents/Real%20Estate/us-expectations-market-reality-real-estate.pdf>
- Deloitte. (2020, April). *Considerations for the real estate industry*. Retrieved from <https://www2.deloitte.com/content/dam/Deloitte/global/Documents/About-Deloitte/COVID-19/Covid-19-Real-estate-sector-considerations.pdf>
- Ferdig, R. E., Baumgartner, E., Hartshorne, R., Kaplan-Rakowski, R., & Mouza, C. (2020). *Teaching, technology, and teacher education during the covid-19 pandemic: Stories from the field*. Waynesville, NC, USA: Association for the Advancement of Computing in Education (AACE).
- Furnell, S. & Shah, J. N. (2020). Home working and cyber security - an outbreak of unpreparedness. *Computer Fraud & Security*. Retrieved from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7434364/>
- Jairak, K., & Praneetpolgrang, P. (2013). Applying IT governance balanced scorecard and importance-performance analysis for providing IT governance strategy in university. Retrieved from <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/IMCS-08-2012-0036/full/html?skipTracking=true>
- Megahed, N. A., & Ghoneim, E. M. (2020). Antivirus-built environment: Lessons learned from Covid-19 pandemic. *Sustainable Cities and Society*, 61, 102350.
- Mohsin, K. (2020). Cybersecurity in corona virus(covid-19) age. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/344247742>
- PricewaterhouseCoopers. (2020, April 27). The real estate industry faces COVID-19: Options for landlords, REITs and more. Retrieved from <https://www.pwc.com/us/en/industries/financial-services/research-institute/blog/real-estate-industry-faces-covid-19.html>
- Refsdal, A., Solhaug, B. & Stolen, K. (2015). *Cyber-Risk Management*. SpringerLink.
- Rosenbaum, E. (2020). Phishing scams, spam spike as hackers use coronavirus to prey on remote workers, stressed IT systems. CNBC. Retrieved from <https://www.cnn.com/2020/03/20/phishing-spam-spike-as-hackers-usecoronavirus-to-hit-remote-work.html>
- Sarginson, N. (2020). Securing your remote workforce against new phishing attacks. *Computer Fraud & Security*. Retrieved from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1361372320300968>
- Teuben, B., & Neshat, R. (2020, June). *Real estate market size 2019*. Retrieved from <https://www.msci.com/documents/10199/035f2439-e28e-09c8-2a78-4c096e92e622>
- Theurillat, T., Rérat, P., & Crevoisier, O. (2013). *The real estate markets: players, institutions and territories*. Retrieved from <https://core.ac.uk/reader/208874050>
- Weill, P. (2004). Don't Just Lead, Govern: How Top-Performing Firms Govern IT. Retrieved from https://tilburguniversity.instructure.com/courses/5142/files/576574?module_item_id=136825

Appendix 1. UML Use Case Diagram & PRE, CURRENT, POST COVID Activity Diagram

UML case diagram

PRE-COVID:

DURING- COVID

POST-COVID

